

Origins of the International Criminal Court

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Abstract

The earliest effort for the creation of the International Criminal Court was made by the committee of jurists which drafted the Statute of Permanent Court of International Justice in 1920 and recommended for the establishment of an International Criminal Court to try crimes against International Public Order. League of National adopted a Convention for the establishment of an International Criminal Court in 1937 but it never came into force. General Assembly of the United Nations adopted the Rome Statute on International Criminal Court. Finally the Court was inaugurated on March 11, 2003 in the Haque with swearing-in of its judges.

Keywords: Convention, Treaty, Statute, Criminal Court.

Introduction

With development of the law of armed conflict in the mid-nineteenth century, concepts of international prosecution for humanitarian abuses slowly began to emerge. One of the founders of the Red Cross movement, which grew up in Geneva in the 1860s, urged a draft statute for an international criminal court. Its task would be to prosecute breaches of the Geneva Convention of 1864 and other humanitarian norms. But Gustav Monnier's innovative proposal was much too radical for its time.

The Hague Conventions of 1899 and 1907 represent the first significant codification of the laws of war in an international treaty. They include an important series of provisions dealing with the protection of civilian populations. Article 46 of the Regulations that are annexed to the Hague Convention IV of 1907 enshrines the respect of 'family honour and rights, the lives of persons, and private property, as well as religious convictions and practice'. Other provisions of the Regulations protect cultural objects and private property of civilians. The preamble to the Conventions recognizes that they are incomplete, but promises that until a more complete code of the laws of war is issued, 'the inhabitants and the belligerents remain under the protection and the rule of the principles of the law of nations, as they result from the usages established among civilized peoples, from the laws of humanity, and the dictates of the public conscience'. This provision is known as the Martens clause, after the Russian diplomat who drafted it.

The Hague Conventions, as international treaties, were meant to impose obligations and duties upon States, and were not intended to create criminal liability for individuals. They declared certain acts to be illegal, but not criminal, as can be seen from the absence of anything suggesting a sanction for their violation. Yet within only a few years, the Hague Conventions were being presented as a source of the law of war crimes.

Origins of the International Criminal Court

The Rome conference to establish the International Criminal Court started with a few formal speeches from several legal luminaries and important political figures, United Nations officials and personalities from the growing ranks of those actually involved in international criminal prosecution, including the presidents of the two ad hoc tribunals and their Prosecutor. Then the Conference divided into a series of working groups with responsibility for matters such as general principles, procedure and penalties. Much of this involved details, unlikely to create insurmountable difficulties to the extent that the delegates were committed to the success of the endeavour. But a handful of core issues – jurisdiction, the 'trigger mechanism' for prosecutions, the role of the Security Council – remained under the wing of the Bureau. These difficult questions were not publicly debated for most of the Conference, although much negotiating took place informally. In addition to the Statute of the International Criminal Court, on 17 July, 1998 the Diplomatic Conference also adopted a Final Act, providing for the establishment of a Preparatory Commission. The Commission was assigned a variety of tasks,

of which the most important were the drafting of the Rules of Procedure and Evidence, which provide details on a variety of procedural and evidentiary questions, and the Elements of Crimes, which elaborate upon the definitions of offences in Articles 6, 7 and 8 of the Statute. The Commission met the deadline of 30 June 2000 set for it by the Final Act, for the completion of the Rules and the Elements. Other tasks include drafting an agreement with the United Nations on the relationship between the two organizations, and preparation of a host state agreement with the Netherlands, which is to be the seat of the Court. The Preparatory Commission is to operate until the Statute comes into force, at which point the Assembly of States Parties will be convened. The Assembly will elect the judges and prosecutor, and presumably endorse the work of the Preparatory Commission.

The international Criminal Court is perhaps the most innovative and exciting development in international law since the creation of the United Nations. The Statute is one of the most complex international instruments ever negotiated, a sophisticated web of highly technical provisions drawn from comparative criminal law combined with a series of more political propositions that touch the very heart of State concerns with their own sovereignty. Without any doubt its creation is the result of the human rights agenda that has steadily taken centre stage within the United Nations since Article 1 of its Charter proclaimed the promotion of human rights to be one of its purposes. From a hesitant commitment in 1945, to an ambitious Universal Declaration of Human Rights in 1948, we have now reached a point where individual criminal liability is established for those responsible for serious violations of human rights, and where an institution is created to see that this is more than just some pious wish.

Overview of the International Criminal Court

The Rome Statute established a permanent International Criminal Court (ICC) with the power to investigate and prosecute those who commit genocide, crimes against humanity, war crimes and aggression. Its adoption on 17 July 1998 and the subsequent speedy entry into force on 1 July 2002 represent a significant achievement for the world community. One hundred and twenty States out of the 160 or so that assembled in Rome for the United Nations conference voted in support of the Statute's final text. Subsequently, 139 States signed the Statute, and currently 123 States from every region and legal system of the world have become Parties to the Statute. The creation of the Court therefore represents the realization of a strong consensus among States - a remarkable feat, considering the various interests and legal systems that contributed to the process, as well as the fact that the United Nations General Assembly had first addressed this question over 50 years ago. Not only is the ICC a principal means of combating impunity, it promises to contribute to the preservation, restoration and maintenance of international peace and security.

The Court has been operational for about twenty years, with the judges, Prosecutors and Registrar having taken up their offices in the Court's facilities in The Hague in the Netherlands. The Court has built up much of its internal administration procedures and is now well into the exercise of its judicial activities at the pre-trial and appeals level. The Court has issued arrest warrants for suspects of atrocities in Uganda, Democratic Republic of the Congo and Darfur in Sudan, has three suspects in custody in The Hague and has also issued important decisions elaborating on the rights for victims to act as participants in judicial proceedings. ICC's first hearing held in 2006, was to decide whether charges should be brought Thomas Lubanga, who was accused of recruiting child soldiers in the Democratic Republic of Congo.

The place of the ICC in the international legal system

The ICC fills a significant void in the international legal system. First, unlike the International Court of Justice, which is concerned with issues of State responsibility, the ICC has jurisdiction over individuals. Furthermore, unlike tribunals those have been established by the United Nations Security Council on an ad hoc basis, such as the International Criminal Tribunals for the Former Yugoslavia and for Rwanda (ICTY/R) or "hybrid" tribunals such as those in East Timor, Sierra Leone or Cambodia, which have been created to respond to specific situations and exist for a limited time period, the ICC is a permanent body with a much broader mandate. As a treaty based institution, the ICC has a unique relationship with the United Nations system. The Negotiated Relationship Agreement between the ICC and the United Nations, signed in October 2004, establishes the legal foundation for cooperation between the two organizations within their respective mandates.

The ICC is intended to complement, not be a substitute for, national criminal justice systems. This "principle of complementarity" ensures that the Court will intervene only in those cases where national courts are unable or unwilling to initiate or conduct their own proceedings. (These circumstances are carefully defined in the Statute,

article 17(1)). The Court will not, therefore, encroach on an individual State's jurisdiction over crimes covered by the Statute.

Scope of the ICC

Article 5 of the Statute lists the crimes that are within the jurisdiction of the Court: genocide, crimes against humanity, war crimes and the crime of aggression. Article 6 defines the crime of genocide for the purposes of ICC prosecutions in substantially the same way as it is currently defined under article 2 of the Genocide Convention 1948. Both crimes against humanity (Article 7) and war crimes (Article 8) have been carefully defined in the Statute to mostly incorporate crimes from different treaty and customary sources, which 120 States at the Rome Conference agreed were “the most serious crimes of concern to the international community as a whole” (article 5).

Currently, the Court exercises jurisdiction over all the listed crimes except aggression. Article 5(2) provides that the Court shall exercise jurisdiction over the crime of aggression once a provision is adopted in accordance with article 121 and 123, defining the crime and setting out conditions under which the Court shall exercise jurisdiction with respect to the crime. Such a provision must be consistent with the Charter of the United Nations.

The procedural provisions of the Rome Statute have been drafted in an effort to create a balance between the following priorities:

- The need for an independent, apolitical, representative international Court, which can function efficiently and effectively to bring to justice those responsible for the most serious crimes of concern to the international community as a whole.
- The right of States to take primary responsibility for prosecuting such crimes if they are genuinely willing and able.
- The need to give victims of such crimes adequate redress and compensation. The need to protect the rights of accused persons.
- The role of the Security Council in maintaining international peace and security in accordance with its powers under Chapter VII of the Charter of the United Nations.

These considerations are all reflected in the functions and powers of the Court, and in its relationship with other entities, as set out under the Statute.

The structure of the Court

The ICC is composed of the following organs: the Presidency, the Judicial Divisions, the Office of the Prosecutor, and the Registry (article 34). The Presidency is responsible for the proper administration of the Court, with the exception of the Office of the Prosecutor (article 38). The Judicial Divisions, made up of the Pre-Trial Division, the Trial Division, and the Appeals Division, consist of 18 judges who are elected by the Assembly of States Parties, by a two-thirds majority of those present and voting, based on nominations made by States Parties (article 36(6)). The Registry is responsible for the non-judicial aspects of the administration and servicing of the Court and the Registrar is elected by the judges (article 43). This includes the establishment of a Victims and Witnesses Unit within the Registry, which employs staff with expertise in trauma [article 43(6)]. The Registry also has responsibilities relating to the rights of the defense (article 43(1), rules 20 and 21, Rules of Procedure and Evidence). Regulations of the Registry were adopted in March 2006. Staff Regulations in September 2003 and the Code of Professional Conduct for Counsel in December 2005.

The Prosecutor and Deputy Prosecutors are elected by the Assembly of States Parties based on criteria similar to that for judges (article 42). The Office of the Prosecutor is responsible for receiving referrals and information on crimes within the jurisdiction of the Court, examining and analyzing that information, and conducting investigations and prosecutions. The Office of the Prosecutor has issued a Policy Paper and Regulations that, in part, highlight the priority tasks and set out an institutional framework to ensure independence and accountability. Other documents issued by the Office of the Prosecutor include an Annex to the Policy Paper on Communications and Referrals and a Policy Paper on the Interests of Justice; the latter sets out the Office's understanding of the concept of the interests of justice as mentioned in article 53 of the Statute.

The ICC judges, Prosecutor, Deputy Prosecutors and the Registrar are independent in the performance of their functions, and the Statute provides that they should be accorded the same privileges and immunities as heads of

diplomatic missions when carrying out the business of the Court (article 48). However, they may be removed from office for serious misconduct or a serious breach of any, of their duties under the Statute (article 46).

How a case is brought to trial

Upon the application of the Prosecutor, the Pre-Trial Chamber decides whether or not to issue a warrant for the arrest and surrender of a person suspected of committing an ICC crime. The Statute sets out a number of factors that the Chamber must take into account before issuing such a warrant, including reasonable grounds to believe that the person committed the crime that is under investigation (article 58). States Parties are required to assist the Court in executing requests to arrest and surrender persons to the ICC (articles 59 and 89). Once the person is brought before the Court, either voluntarily or by means of a warrant, the Pre-Trial Chamber must hold a confirmation hearing to ensure that the Prosecutor has sufficient evidence to support each charge [article 61(5)]. The person is entitled to apply for interim release at several stages in the pre-trial phase [articles 59(3) and 60(2)]. There are also several opportunities for the accused, the Prosecutor and the States to ask the Pre-Trial Chamber to review various decisions of the Prosecutor and to appeal certain decisions of the Pre-Trial Chamber prior to the commencement of a trial (for example, see articles 19 and 53).

General principles of criminal law

The Statute incorporates existing international standards and principles for the prosecution of crimes. For example, no person will be prosecuted or punished by the ICC for any conduct that did not constitute a crime or did not carry such a punishment, at the time the conduct was performed (articles 22 and 23). In addition, no person will be prosecuted by the ICC for any conduct that formed the basis of crimes for which the person has already been convicted or acquitted by the Court, or by another court, unless the proceeding in another court were for the purpose of shielding that person from criminal responsibility, or were not conducted independently or impartially in accordance with the norms of due process recognized by international law, and were conducted in a manner that was inconsistent with an intent to bring the person to justice (article 20).

Furthermore, the application and interpretation of the applicable law must be consistent with internationally recognized human rights. Article 26 also provides that no person who was under the age of 18 at the time of the alleged crime will be prosecuted.

The Statute provides for individual criminal responsibility, including responsibility as an accessory or accomplice to a crime, or other similar involvement in the commission or attempted commission of a crime (article 25). Under article 25(1), the Court has jurisdiction over natural persons only. This means that corporations cannot be indicted or tried by the ICC. However, this restriction is not to be confused with the responsibility of corporate officers and employees, who can be held individually criminally responsible for genocide, crimes against humanity and war crimes or responsible as “commanders” or “superiors” under article 28.

The Statute provides for the rights of the accused as well as victims and witnesses (articles 63 and 66 to 70). The rights of the accused to a fair and public hearing are to be conducted in accordance with standards that are derived from the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and other widely accepted international instruments. These include the following rights:

- The accused must be present during the trial.
- The accused' is entitled to be presumed innocent until proven guilty before the Court in accordance with the applicable law.
- The Prosecutor has the onus to prove the guilt of the accused and must persuade the Court of the guilt of the accused beyond a reasonable doubt.
- The Court's decisions must be in writing and contain reasons and sentences pronounced publicly and in the presence of the accused, wherever possible.

Vulnerable witnesses and victims will also be protected during any proceedings and the Court will decide which evidence is admissible. Victims may make presentations to the Court at various stages of the proceedings, either in person or through their legal counsel.

The Statute also allows for appeals against various decisions of the Trial Chamber, such as a decision to convict or to impose a particular sentence on a person (articles 81 to 84).

The Court may impose one of the following penalties on a convicted person:

- Imprisonment for a maximum of 30 years.
- A term of life imprisonment when justified by the extreme gravity of the crime and the individual circumstances of the convicted person..
- In addition, the Court may order:
- A fine.
- A forfeiture of the proceeds, property and assets derived directly or indirectly from that crime (article 77).

Finally, the Court may order the convicted person to pay reparations to victims, in the form of restitution, compensation or rehabilitation [article 75(2)].

Conclusion

The Court will rely on States to provide cooperation and assistance throughout the investigation, prosecution and punishment process, as necessary (articles 86 to 103). States Parties are required to respond to requests for assistance from the Court unless genuine national security interests would be threatened (article 72) and in certain other very limited circumstances. States Parties may also be required to help enforce fines and forfeiture orders or reparations orders (articles 75(5) and 109). In addition, any State may volunteer to accept and supervise sentenced persons (articles 103 to 107). However, such States may not modify the sentence of the person or release the person before expiry of the sentence pronounced by the Court (articles 105 and 110).

The reality is that the Court does not possess an international police force of its own and relies on States to perform all cooperation tasks. The Court has submitted a report to the Bureau of the Assembly of States Parties that identified areas of cooperation needed. These included the adoption of domestic implementing legislation, support for the enforcement of the Court's decisions such as arrest and surrender; and diverse forms of practical cooperation such as victim protection and support, logistics and security.

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